

Stranger things: The vanishing of the altmetric attention score values in information and library science

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Abstract

Altmetrics encompass a broad set of metrics derived from the multiple interactions produced around science in social media. It is a complex and liquid phenomenon that is further complicated by the creation of proposals such as the *Altmetric Attention Score* (AAS). However, there are only studies that analyze the accumulation of mentions in different sources but without considering the volatility of these and their impact on such aggregated metrics. Our main objective is to study how the *Altmetric Attention Score* value fluctuates over time. For this we use a set of 73,367 scholarly outputs published between 2012 and 2021 and indexed in the *Web of Science* Information Science & Library Science category. We then queried the DOIs of these publications on *Altmetric.com* monthly between February 2022 and July 2022 to obtain their *Altmetric Attention Score*. Thus, changes in this metric were studied for 26,474 ISLS publications with altmetrics mentions over 6 months. As a result, we found that in this period 10% of the publications have reduced their AAS value. A metric anomaly has been identified both at the paper level and at the category level.

Introduction

Citations have been extensively studied since the very beginning of scientometrics. It has made possible not only to analyze science through scientific literature but also to know the particular characteristics of this metric, such as its skewed distribution (Price, 1965; Seglen, 1992) or life cycles (Burton & Kebler, 1960). Furthermore, there are also several metrics derived from citations and directly oriented to the evaluation of scientific performance, such as the *Impact Factor*. However, the advent of altmetrics has altered this citation-dominated paradigm, with the emergence of a wide range of social media metrics (Priem et al., 2010). Since the first moment, attempts have been made to find a relationship between altmetrics and citations without success (Thelwall et al., 2013). This is a completely different phenomenon, marked by a wide variety of sources, each one with a different nature, and above all the evanescence of these mentions, which is not the case with citations.

Altmetrics englobe a broad set of metrics derived from the multiple interactions produced around science in social media (Díaz-Faes et al., 2019). This makes it possible to capture science-related interactions outside of the scientific realm, but at the same time they are completely platform-dependent. That is why this activity can be faded out with the cessation of the activity or the discontinuation of the platform itself, e.g., *Google+*. In addition to the variety of sources is the fact that altmetrics are extracted from each of their platforms, with multiple strategies in place. Altmetrics data aggregators such as *Altmetric.com* or *Crossref Event Data* differ greatly for this reason, offering different levels of coverage for the same source (Zahedi & Costas, 2018). There are also differences between countries (Torres-Salinas et al., 2022). In addition to all these limitations, there is also the volatility of the mentions of some of them. On *Twitter*, not only the stability of tweets mentioning scholarly outputs has been studied (Fang et al., 2020), understood as their unavailability over time, but also how

such tweets become available again (Fang et al., 2022), similar phenomenon has also been identified with *Wikipedia* references (Arroyo-Machado et al., 2020).

Altmetrics is a complex and liquid phenomenon that is further complicated by the creation of proposals such as the *Altmetric Attention Score* (AAS) (Altmetric Support, 2021), a weighted metric that aggregates mentions from different sources and whose reading and interpretation is confusing (Thelwall, 2020). This metric has not only been widely criticized for the lack of empirical criteria in the weighting assignment (Gumpenberger et al., 2016; Mukherjee et al., 2018), but the reproducibility of its calculation has also been questioned (Ortega, 2019). Nevertheless, this metric has a strong presence through the *Altmetric.com* badges included in journals, databases and repositories, and is also widely used as a social attention proxy, especially in Health Sciences (Kolahi et al., 2021). That is why, without disregarding its limitations, it cannot be ignored. Despite all the research done on the *Altmetric Attention Score*, there are no studies that have analyzed the fluctuation of its value. There are only proposals that analyze the accumulation of mentions from different sources (Fang & Costas, 2020), but without considering the volatility of these and their impact on the *Altmetric Attention Score*.

The main objective of this paper is to explore over time the performance of an altmetric indicator such as the *Altmetric Attention Score* by monitoring its possible variations.

The specific objectives are the following:

- *Objective 1.* Calculate the *Altmetric Attention Score* values of Information Science & Library Science (ISLS) publications during six months at paper-level.
- *Objective 2.* To determine the rate of variability/vanishing during the six months to detect fluctuations at aggregate-level.

Methodology

Table 1. Number of papers analyzed per year published in Information Science & Library Science (Web of Science category) with the detail of papers with *Altmetric Attention Score*

Publication Year	Nr. of Papers	Papers in Altmetric.com	Papers with AAS	% Papers with AAS
2012	6592	2559	1794	27.21%
2013	7094	2840	2112	29.77%
2014	6697	2740	2174	32.46%
2015	6562	2986	2397	36.53%
2016	7319	3323	2775	37.92%
2017	8007	3801	2906	36.29%
2018	7364	3550	2868	38.95%
2019	7852	3684	3027	38.55%
2020	8392	3743	3293	39.24%
2021	7488	3355	3128	41.77%
Total	73,367	32,581	26,474	36.08%

In order to overcome the above commented limitations in the study of an altmetric indicator, especially the *Altmetric Attention Score* (Thelwall, 2020), the sample of publications used is related to the same scientific category and takes into account their different publication dates. On 1st February 2022, bibliographic records of publications indexed in the *Web of Science*

Information Science & Library Science category (ISLS) were retrieved from Clarivate's *Incites*. ESCI publications were included and the query was limited to the period 2012-2021 and the citable document typologies article, letter and review. A total of 73,367 documents were collected. This dataset of ISLS publications was used as the basis for an iterative altmetrics data retrieval process. From February 2022 to July 2022, on the first day of each month, the DOIs of these 73,367 ISLS publications were queried on *Altmetric.com* to retrieve their *Altmetric Attention Score* values and altmetrics mentions. Thus, for this dataset of ISLS publications 6 monthly (February, March, April, May, June, and July) snapshots with data downloaded from *Altmetric.com* were generated.

Table 1 provides an overview of the data used in this paper. In total we have identified 32,581 ISLS publications indexed in *Altmetric.com* but only those with an *Altmetric Attention Score* greater than 0 were used, giving a total of 26,474 (36% of the total). The sample we used only considers papers with an AAS of at least 1 in order to be able to observe not only increases but, above all, decreases in this metric over time. Table 1 shows that the number of publications with AAS is increasing yearly; in 2012 it was only 27% and in 2021 it reached the highest value of 41%. Once the data were collected to study possible changes in AAS values, two analyses were conducted. First, a paper-by-paper analysis was performed to observe the differences in AAS values between February 2022 and July 2022, noting in each one of them whether this value remained the same or if there had been an increase or decrease. Second, a data aggregate analysis was performed, differentiating by month of observation and year of publication. In this analysis, the percentage increase in the AAS with respect to the previous month observed was calculated, denominating this value as *AAS Monthly Variability Rate* (AMVR).

Results

Paper-by-paper analysis

Figure 1. Plot of *Altmetric Attention Score* values in February 2022 and July 2022 (log-log). Note: All values have been increased by 1 to represent the 297 cases with an AAS of zero.

Figure 1 shows the fluctuation in AAS between the first altmetric data collection in February 2022 (x-axis) and the last one in July 2022 (y-axis) for the 26,474 Web of Science documents analyzed. Three possible statuses of the items have been depicted in the graph: (1) on the diagonal (yellow points) are the publications that at both times have the same AAS value; (2) above it are those that have increased (blue points); and (3) below it is those that have decreased (red points). Here we find that 1645 publications (6.21% of the total) have increased their AAS in July 2022 with respect to February 2022, 2694 (10.18%) have reduced it, and 22,135 have kept it the same (83.61%). We are therefore faced with an important metric anomaly. A total of 939 of these works have seen their value reduced moderately or significantly, i.e. with changes of more than 25%. It should be noted also that among the publications that reduce their AAS, there are 297 (1.12%) that totally lose it, falling to zero.

Aggregate papers analysis

Table 2 shows the aggregate AAS data for ISLS publications. At the category level, a certain stability with a tendency to growth is observed. Thus, for the set of papers published between 2012-2021 their aggregate AAS value is in February 276,290 and in July 278,665. However, this general growth does not occur for publications in all years or in all months studied. Thus, in July there is a generalized decrease for all years, with the exception of 2020 and 2021, in the same way that the more recent the publications are, the higher the values.

Table 2. Aggregated values values for the *Altmetric Attention Score* for Information Science and Library Science publications

	Feb 2022	Mar 2022	Apr 2022	May 2022	Jun 2022	Jul 2022
<i>Publication Year</i>	Aggregated values of the Altmetric Attention Score					
<i>2012</i>	13,649	13,822	13,840	13,894	13,909	13,431
<i>2013</i>	15,562	15,578	15,714	15,706	15,749	15,169
<i>2014</i>	19,175	19,180	19,198	19,224	19,246	18,506
<i>2015</i>	28,232	28,290	28,316	28,351	28,367	28,158
<i>2016</i>	29,143	29,290	29,323	29,332	29,362	29,190
<i>2017</i>	32,011	32,093	32,226	32,278	32,435	32,241
<i>2018</i>	34,413	34,429	34,504	34,417	34,490	34,465
<i>2019</i>	34,703	34,771	34,845	35,034	35,345	35,335
<i>2020</i>	39,091	39,321	39,536	39,697	39,972	40,108
<i>2021</i>	30,311	30,947	31,204	31,364	31,757	32,062
<i>Total</i>	276,290	277,721	278,706	279,297	280,632	278,665

Figure 2 shows the *AAS Monthly Variability Rate (AMVR)* of the publications studied. The pattern is not the same for all years. It can be seen that the oldest publications show a very low growth and even losses at certain times. The generalized decrease in the number of mentions in July 2022 stands out. Overall reductions in AAS were identified during the months of June and July. These declines are not the same every year. During the years 2012, 2013 and 2014 is when the most important reductions and a higher value of AAS are identified. For example, in 2014 the aggregate value of AAS is reduced by up to 5%. This effect is smaller in more recent years'

Figure 2. AAS Monthly Variability Rate (AMVR) rate of Information Science & Library Science publications between March and July 2022 by year of publication

Conclusions

There is no doubt about the limitations of the Altmetric Attention Score at the moment. This aggregated metric does not take into account the nature and specificities of each social media (Thelwall, 2020), the weight assigned to mentions is not justified (Gumpenberger et al., 2016; Mukherjee et al., 2018) and its replication is not entirely possible (Ortega, 2019). However, as with other metrics, the fact that it is not free of limitations does not make it invisible to the community, nor does it mean that it is not used. The Altmetric Attention Score can thus be seen as the equivalent of the Journal Impact Factor or h-Index, because despite their well-known limitations, both bibliometric indicators are widely used as general proxies of academic impact. This scenario consequently demands greater efforts to further explore the characteristics and behavior of this metric. In this article we have found that there are 2694 publications (10.18% of the total) that have reduced their AAS values.

A metric anomaly has been identified both at the paper level and for the aggregate values of the category. Therefore, this study is still under development and will be completed in the future. Firstly, the six months studied will be expanded to a full year (from February 2022 to February 2023) and the periods studied will be divided into fortnights instead of months. Secondly, in addition to the Altmetric Attention Score, the fluctuation in specific altmetric sources will also be studied to identify what social media affect this loss of AAS and the reasons for it. Thirdly, in addition to the use of papers published up to 2021 we are also analyzing ISLS papers that are being published through 2022. Ultimately, a complete longitudinal dataset will be generated with data retrieved from Altmetric.com every 15 days throughout 2022 for both ISLS papers published between 2012 to 2021 and those that have been published during 2022. This will allow us to conduct a much more complete statistical analysis, providing a more comprehensive overview of the altmetrics fluctuations, particularly with regards to the loss of mentions. With this analysis we expect to determine which altmetric sources are the most volatile and whose fluctuations have the greatest impact on the instability of the Altmetric Attention Score, as well as to identify whether the loss of mentions increases over time.

Acknowledgments

Funding: PID2019-109127RB-I00/SRA/10.13039/501100011033 and FPU18/05835.

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